

Peumus boldus

Cluster 1 (n=4)

Cluster 2 (n=4)

Cluster 3 (n=10)

Cluster 4 (n=9)

Cryptocarya alba

Cluster 1 (n=6)

Cluster 2 (n=11)

Cluster 3 (n=8)

Cluster 4 (n=5)

